

PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS OF EDUCATION OF PRIMARY SCHOOL CHILDREN THROUGH MUSIC

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INTRODUCTION. Small school age of children's personal, social and emotional development, music, science through train efficiency depends. Music, children's sensitivities, aesthetic appearance and creative abilities in the development of an important role plays. In addition, music education is important in the formation of children's social skills and their integration into society. In this article, a small school for young children music science through educating pedagogical conditions of the review is out.

MAIN PART. A small school for young children's development of every one of the aspects one with associated is, music of this process, the role is incomparable. Music, children 's emotional, social, cognitive and physical development of large effect shows. Music, children aesthetic things, that beautiful harmonious feel to make and it accept to abilities in the development of help will.

Aesthetic education, music through the children of glory, irritability and creativity, a sense of shape.

Emotional development. Music, children 's emotional world expansion to serve will. Music listening to, of the execution to or creation through children, their feelings, their express and others understand the ability to development. Music helps children to recognize and understand different emotions, such as joy, sadness, and excitement. Children's music listening by their emotions management and represent the ability to form.

Music, children between social relationships development are also important. Music activities children for each other to help, to give, the thoughts you share and their thoughts express to the opportunity it gives.

A small school for young children music science through nurturing for a comfortable environment to create the needed. Music to read for a peaceful and calm environment to create, children to the attention fruitful and creative to engage in life increase for is important. The use of modern visual aids in music education increases children's interest and intensifies the learning process.

Music science teacher for the children in bringing up an important role plays. His professional training and spiritual value to children's music education to be given and effective up to for an important condition is one of. The teacher knows music theory, composition, performance and history well. The teacher must have the ability to understand the psychological characteristics of children, communicate with them and adapt to their needs. Family environment and social relationships of children's music to subject the interest forms. Parents music to the relationship, children music education , the interest increases.

Parents of active ministry: parents of music in education, active participation, of the child's creative activity in the development of an important role to have. Music festivals, concerts , and family events of children to music on the interest and of them the creative abilities to develop.

Interactive teaching methods, children 's active participation to and them creative abilities to develop to help will. Thus:

Group work: Encourages children to work together and cooperate.

Role games: Music to science related role games, kids music in practice enable the opportunity to gives.

Multimedia tools, music education new opportunities in the creation of a are used. Videos, interactive software and online resources for children's interest in increasing help will.

CONCLUSION. A small school for young children music science through educating, their personal and social development is an important role you have. Music, children 's emotional, social, cognitive and physical development in a positive way ta'secret ko'rsat is. Music through children's own feel-feelings express it to, others with cooperate to, mind analysis to make , and physical activity development will learn. This is the reason for, a small school of youth for music education effective for the organization to, in their full development service will.

Pedagogical conditions, family environment and modern teaching methods for children, music education effective results progress in ensuring an important role plays. This process, of the child's creative abilities, develop , and them aesthetic to educate, serve, will.

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